

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 4 – 12 November 2024

Report published: May 2025

**Elephant encounters:
Studying Asian elephants in the hills of
northern Thailand to increase their
welfare and conservation**

มูลนิธิหัวใจรักช้าง
Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary
Love. Care. Rescue.

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**Authors:
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**Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions**

Abstract

Since 2016 Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) has conducted a research and conservation project in Northern Thailand (Mae Chaem District) on a herd of semi-wild elephants (*Elephas maximus*). From 2018 onwards Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists and KSES research interns have helped with data collection. This report combines digitally recorded data by Biosphere expedition citizen scientists from 4 – 12 November 2024, as well as data collected by KSES interns throughout 2024. It also provides an overview of the results over the years and concludes the successful KSES / Biosphere Expeditions partnership as KSES shifts its focus to publishing the behavioural data collected to date.

The observational study encompassed four distinct datasets on six free-roaming semi-wild Asian elephants: (1) Activity Budgets with continuous and instantaneous sampling, (2) Foraging Ecology via all-occurrence focal sampling, (3) Social Association via scan sampling and (4) Calf Development with continuous and instantaneous sampling.

Analyses of 29,622 continuous Activity Budget sampling minutes showed that elephants spent most of their time foraging (72%), followed by exploring (5%). The behaviour counts of instantaneous Activity Budget sampling showed that the elephants spent most of their time foraging (72%), exploring (23%) and dusting (7%). Further analyses showed that there is a statistically significant difference between dusting, exploring and scratching and the 16 other behaviours in both continuous and instantaneous data, such as bathing, aggression, lying down and mating, which were all recorded at below 1%. Overall, the activity budgets of the KSES herd are much closer to those observed in wild, rather than captive elephants.

7,089 minutes of Foraging Ecology data revealed that the elephants consume a diverse diet, comprising 63 plant species. They spent most of their time consuming graze species (66%), followed by browse species (34%). Whilst little is known of the natural foraging ecology of elephants in Thailand, it is clear that the KSES herd consumes a much more varied diet than captive elephants, for which datasets exist. KSES and Biosphere Expeditions encourage those in the elephant industry to recognise the important link between diet and welfare, and to introduce a more varied and richer diet for elephants. Results from the Social Associations dataset elucidated complex social interactions within the herd, with females having a larger percentage of interactions, which corroborates other studies. In June 2023 a baby calf was born into the herd, resulting in an unexpected shift in social interactions. Other studies have shown that elephant mothers and other female family members have been observed to provide social support to newborns for normal development. Interestingly, in the KSES herd, the parents remain close and somewhat segregated, with the father closely involved in rearing. KSES aims to publish a scientific paper on this in 2025.

5,626 minutes of continuous data collected in the most recently added dataset of Calf Development showed that the herd's juvenile "Junior" spent most of his time foraging and exploring (48%), and interacting with the mahouts (elephant caretakers) (4%). The counts of instantaneous behaviours showed that the most frequent behaviours were again foraging and exploring (35%), elephant interaction (11%) followed closely by mahout interaction (9%). This is to be expected, as the young elephant calf is exploring his surroundings under the guidance of the rest of the herd as well as the mahouts, who are there to protect and watch over the elephants at KSES. Elephants have strong family bonds and many members of the herd watch over the young. That this is displayed at KSES is another clear indication of natural behaviour dominance.

Overall, analyses provide clear evidence that KSES elephants are closer to wild, rather than captive, elephants in all aspects studied. This shows that KSES's hands-off and semi-wild approach to elephant husbandry results in high animal welfare in near-natural conditions. To publicise this, KSES aims to publish welfare guidelines in 2026. Since the elephant industry is by and large profit-driven, the welfare guidelines will also describe easy and cost-effective ways to cultivate plants such as grasses and bamboo for the consumption of elephants in captivity.

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1. Expedition Review

Matthias Hammer (editor)
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location conditions and the research area are as per Johncola et al. (2019). This expedition conducted close-encounter studies on a herd of six Asian elephants at Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) in the hills of Northern Thailand. All studies were solely observational with no interaction between the elephants and researchers.

1.2. Dates & team

The expedition ran over an 8-day period from 4 to 12 November 2024 and concluded the partnership between KSES and Biosphere Expeditions, as KSES shifts its focus to publishing the behavioral data collected to date.

The expedition team was composed of national and international citizen scientists, a professional scientist and an expedition leader. The study period was chosen to coincide with the mildest climate in terms of temperature extremes and high forest food availability for the elephants.

The expedition scientist and primary author of this report was Laura Peoples, the expedition leader was Roland Arnison. The expedition team of citizen scientists was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence): Jim Blomgren (USA), Stephen Crowther (UK), Edward Durell (Germany), Rachel Fischer (USA), Neele Hülsemann (Germany), Brandon Hwang (USA), Anette Lafaire (Germany).

A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not need to be invoked as there were no medical or other incidences.

1.3. Partners

On this expedition Biosphere Expeditions' main partner was KSES, a fellow non-profit organisation. Their main objective is to bring elephants back to their natural environment to live in semi-wild conditions and provide an alternative and sustainable livelihood.

1.4. Acknowledgements

First and foremost, Biosphere Expeditions would like to express its sincere gratitude to KSES for a successful partnership from 2017 to 2024 and wishes KSES all the best for its future endeavours. We are grateful to the citizen scientists, who not only dedicated their spare time to helping but also, through their expedition contributions, funded the research. A big thank you to all the members of the local community, especially those who welcomed expedition participants into their homes with open arms, who guided us through the forest, who helped with transportation and who cooked amazing meals. Finally, Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank members of the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions and donors for their support.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

Project updates, reports and publications:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

All expedition reports, including this and previous expedition reports:

<https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Expedition diary/blog:

<https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/thailand-2024/>

Expedition details, background, pictures, videos, etc.

<https://www.biosphere-expeditions.org/expedition-archive#thailand>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each citizen scientist paid a contribution of €2,360 per person per nine-day group towards expedition costs. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	18,888
Expenditure	
Staff	3,759
includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	
Research	144
includes equipment and other research expenses	
Transport	503
includes fuel, taxis and other local transport	
Expedition base	1,896
includes board & lodging and base hut upgrade	
Administration	334
includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	
Team recruitment Thailand	9,768
as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	
Income – Expenditure	2,484
Total percentage spent directly on project	87%

2. Activity budgeting, foraging and social behaviour of free-roaming semi-wild Asian elephants

Laura Peoples
Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary

2.1. Introduction

Asian elephants *Elephas maximus* are of great cultural significance in Thailand dating back to as early as the 13th century (Bansiddhi et al. 2020, Baker & Winkler 2020). Their role has changed over the years from being used in warfare, the logging industry, in cultural and religious traditions, to more recently in the tourism industry. The latter is the most predominant activity for elephants today, since logging was banned in Thailand in 1989 (Bansiddhi et al. 2019). Many captive elephants were working in the logging industry before this ban. This industry was a main contributor to the deforestation in Thailand, coupled with an increasing demand for agricultural land. Following the ban, working elephants were out of work and out of a home as there was not enough forested habitat to go back to and what was left is extremely fragmented (Nijman 2014). This not only affected the captive elephant population, but also affected wild elephants, as they could no longer roam through forest throughout their native range. This negatively impacted elephant foraging habits, as well as migration routes, which resulted in elephants coming into human settlements, creating human-elephant conflict (Zakaria et al. 2024). As a result, the Thai government began to classify elephant populations into wild and captive elephants. Wild elephants were placed under the protection of the Wild Animal Reservation and Protection Act in 1992, which prohibited capturing, killing and injuring elephants (Nijman 2014). There are approximately 4000-4400 wild elephants in Thailand currently (Department of Wildlife National Parks and Plant Conservation: DNP 2023).

For captive elephants however, it was a very different story. They were not awarded the same protection as wild elephants, as they were placed under the Draught Animal Act of 1939, which does not provide them with animal welfare protection (Nijman 2014). In fact, they are considered livestock, which requires the Thai government to create employment for them. It is estimated that there are currently over 4000 captive elephants in Thailand, many of whom are employed in tourist venues, providing a range of activities to tourists (Sukmasuang et al. 2024, Bansiddhi et al. 2020). Tourism is an extremely important factor in Thailand's economy and there has been an increase in the demand for animal-based tourism, in particular elephant tourism, as these charismatic animals have captured the hearts of tourists who come to Asia (Bansiddhi et al. 2020). Such activities range from riding an elephant, elephant entertainment shows, as well as bathing, feeding or walking with elephants (Bansiddhi et al. 2020). Many facilities that house elephants cannot provide opportunities for elephants to forage, socialise and behave as they would in a more natural environment, which can be detrimental to an elephant's health and wellbeing (Baker & Winkler 2020, Veasey 2019). Elephants are a highly social species with complex needs (Bonaparte-Saller & Mench 2018). Furthermore, they are very important to the ecosystem and are a keystone species due to the role they play in seed dispersal and engineering of the forests that they live in (Haynes 2012). Taking these factors into account, it becomes clear that the complex needs of elephants cannot be met in tightly controlled environments (Ghimire et al. 2024). However, as awareness increases about the welfare of animals, and

in particular elephants, concerns are being raised that many tourism practices can be exploitative and abusive, which has led to conversations about an urgent need for change in the way we manage captive Asian elephants. This has led to a shift in observation-only based activities in relation to elephant tourism (Bansiddhi et al. 20219, Ghamire et al. 2024).

Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES), is an NGO that focuses on creating an alternative option for tourism regarding captive elephants in Thailand. Its aim is to bring back elephants to the forest while providing support to the local community in which the project is based. They do this by offering an observation-only elephant tourism experience, which provides an income for the NGO, the mahouts (elephant caretakers) and the local community. This type of organisation benefits the elephants as the setting they live in allows them to exhibit more choice and control as they are living in a more authentic environment. A guest programme was designed to offer the chance to hike out to observe the elephants in their natural environment. With the addition of a research programme, KSES welcomed Biosphere Expeditions and interns to collect valuable data on four different datasets, each with their own goal in furthering elephant wellbeing. This unique setting allowed researchers, citizen scientists and interns to follow a herd of semi-wild Asian elephants and collect data on their natural behaviours. There were four research areas focused on elephant behaviour, foraging, association and calf development. The Activity Time Budget dataset at KSES seeks to provide evidence that elephants that have been brought back to a natural forest setting can exhibit behaviours resembling more closely those of wild elephants than those in more controlled captive regimes. With the Foraging dataset KSES aims to show that there is a lot of variation in an elephant's diet when given the opportunity to forage in a forested habitat and this variation is essential to the health and wellbeing of the elephant. The Social Association dataset aims to provide vital information about elephant associations and social groupings, highlighting the need for connection in a highly social species. And lastly with the introduction of a new dataset on Calf Development, KSES hopes to contribute to future research on the development of young elephants.

By working with the local community, combined with an integrated research approach, KSES aimed to increase awareness about the complex situation regarding elephants in Asia and raise the standards for elephant welfare, while showcasing that such an approach can benefit both elephants and people alike, as humans and elephants are often portrayed as being in conflict with one another. This project offers an alternative solution inspiring positive change and hope by showing that elephants and humans can live alongside each other. The use of scientific methods and partnership with an organisation such as Biosphere Expeditions to publish its findings, has enabled KSES to reach a wide scientific audience while spreading the message of responsible animal tourism to a worldwide audience. For example, in 2020, KSES published its first research paper on elephant foraging, identifying that the elephants in the forest were consuming over 160 different species of plants (Schwarz et al. 2020). KSES has recently included these data in a book about the foraging behaviour of elephants (in press). In 2025 KSES hopes to publish their next paper on elephant behaviour, followed by a complete elephant welfare guide in 2026. The partnership with Biosphere Expeditions has been instrumental in all this.

2.2 Materials & methods

Elephants and study site

The elephants and study site are as per Johncola et al. (2019).

Kindred Spirit Elephant Sanctuary (KSES) is home to six elephants (Table 2.2a). There are three females in the herd, Too Meh (approx. 60 years old), Mae Doom (late 20s) and Sri Prai (15 years old). There are three males in the herd, Dodo (19 years old), Boon Rott (19 years old) and Junior (1 year old). Too Meh is the mother of Mae Doom, grandmother of Dodo and great grandmother to Junior. Mae Doom is the aunt of Dodo. Junior's parents are Sri Prai, an unrelated female and Dodo. Boon Rott is unrelated to the rest of the herd, but came to KSES at the same time as Too Meh and Mae Doom. Too Meh, Mae Doom and Boon Rott were the first elephants to arrive at KSES in 2016. Dodo joined the project in 2018 and Sri Prai joined in 2022. Junior was born in June 2023 at KSES. All elephants, except the calf (Junior), were previously working in the logging or tourism industry, before coming to KSES. During the day, the elephants are free to roam in approximately 4000 acres of community forest located in the Ban Naklang village, Mae Chaem district, Chiang Mai Province, Thailand. Each elephant, except Junior, has their own mahout (elephant caretaker), who stays with the elephants during the day to ensure they do not go into agricultural fields or surrounding villages. Junior is taken care of by the mahout of his mother, Sri Prai.

Table 2.2a. Elephants in the study herd.

Elephant	Sex	Age (years)
Too Mae	F	60 approx
Mae Doom	F	Late 20s approx
Sri Prai	F	15
Dodo	M	19
Boon Rott	M	19
Junior	M	1

Training

There are currently four datasets at KSES: Activity Time Budget, Foraging, Social Association and Calf Development, the latter beginning in January 2024. Expedition citizen scientists contributed to all of these datasets. The expedition began with a two-day training period. This included a data presentation and a training hike to familiarise the citizen scientists with the hiking conditions, the four datasets, and the expectations of collecting real time data in field conditions (e.g. walking on steep hillsides while recording data). After the training period, citizen scientists signed up for a particular dataset and on which elephant to collect data on for that day. Before the first data collection, all citizen scientists were required to pass an elephant identification and elephant behaviour test prior to collecting data to ensure accurate data collection and quality. Additionally, KSES welcomes interns to the project to collect data on the elephants throughout the year. They are given the same presentations, training hike and elephant identification training before beginning data collection.

Data collection

Data collection at KSES began in 2016, initially with pen and paper and from 2023 digitally, using [KoboCollect](#). This report contains the analysis of data from 6 – 11 November 2024. It includes data collected by Biosphere Expeditions citizen scientists from 5 – 11 November 2024, as well as from interns (science students) and staff that collected data throughout 2024 at KSES.

All data collection took place between the hours of 08:00 and 16:00. For Activity Time Budgets and Calf Development, data collection was divided into two time periods, morning (08:00-12:00) and afternoon (12:00-16:00). The Activity Time Budgets, Foraging and Calf Development datasets were recorded via all occurrence focal sampling. Activity Time Budgets data were divided into continuous and instantaneous data, which are analysed separately. Continuous behaviours are those that are displayed by the elephants for one minute or more, while instantaneous behaviours are those that were exhibited for less than one minute. Data were collected in both the morning and afternoon. The Social Association dataset was recorded via 5-minute scan sampling. For each individual elephant a scan of the nearest neighbour, next neighbour and approximate distances were recorded. The distances were categorised as Touching, Two trunks reach (within 3 metres), One elephant length apart (approximately 6 m), or over 6 m apart. For Activity Time Budgets and Calf Development, the behaviour of each elephant was recorded using a behavioural ethogram provided for each participant (Table 2.2b and 2.2c, respectively). The Calf Development dataset is the most recently deployed, and data collection began in January 2024, when the calf was seven months old. The ethogram for this dataset deviates slightly from the adult elephant ethogram as it was modified to be more specific to the behaviours of a young calf. For the Foraging dataset, a plant list in the local language is provided, as this dataset requires the help and local knowledge from the mahouts. When an elephant was found consuming a plant species, the observer asked the mahout for the name of the plant species in the local Karen language. The Karen name was later converted to common name and scientific name. GPS coordinates were automatically captured by KoboCollect to provide additional information about the plant species. All data collected were solely observational with no interaction between the elephants and researchers.

Statistical analysis

All data were analysed using Microsoft Excel Analysing tools. All statistical analysis methods are as per Butron and Hammer (2023). In the Activity Time Budget dataset and Calf Development dataset, total minutes displaying a specific behaviour were recorded as continuous, whereas all instantaneous behaviours were recorded as counts of activities performed. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed for both to evaluate any significant differences for both continuous and instantaneous behaviours individually.

For Foraging Ecology, each plant species was categorised into specific functional groups such as trees, grasses, shrubs, herbs and bamboo. The functional groups were further classified into browse or graze. Even though bamboo is botanically classified as grass, due to its growth characteristics, bamboo was placed under browse species (following Sukumar 1990, Himmelsbach et al. 2006, Chen et al. 2006, Schwarz et al. 2020). For the purpose of this study, when further diving into functional groups, bamboo was placed into an 'other' category due to the ambiguity in previous papers and the classification of shrub in Joshi

(2009). A statistical analysis was performed via a one-way ANOVA to determine whether a significant preference existed between plant type species (climber, trees, shrubs, herbs, grass, bamboo) amongst the elephants.

Table 2.2b. Behavioural ethogram for Activity Time Budget.

Code ID	Behaviour	Description
AT	Agitation	Showing signs of distress due to external factors (motorbike, other animal, loud sounds), that can be exhibited by walking chaotically, raising tail for 5 seconds or more and vocalizing as a form of stress.
AG	Aggression	Threatening behaviour such as standing with ears fanned out or head high, kicking, bumping, or pushing, hitting trunk on the ground or throwing a tantrum.
BA	Bathing	Whole body is immersed in water or having four limbs in water.
DR	Drinking	Using trunk to take water and placing in mouth.
DU	Dusting	Collection of soil with trunk, and throwing it over body.
EX	Exploring	Exploring the environment such as raising trunk to smell, using trunk on the ground to explore the substrate or other objects. As well as stopping previous behaviour, and moving ears straight up, to listen to their surroundings. Does not include foraging behaviour.
FG	Foraging	Placing food in mouth, exploring environment to find new food. Walking towards food.
EI	Elephant interaction	Interacting with other individuals with touch of any body part (Not part of courtship behaviour).
LD	Lying down	Lying down on the ground laterally.
MI	Mahout interaction	Interaction with mahout, solicited or spontaneous.
MA	Mating	Courting or being courted or mounting another elephant or being mounted by another elephant of either sex
MB	Mud bathing	Rolling in mud or using trunk to spray mud on body.
NV	Not visible	Behaviour cannot be recorded, elephant out of view, or cannot distinguish behaviour.
SC	Scratching	Scratching or rubbing any body part with another part of the body, or with an inanimate object
SV	Social vocalising	Communication such as rumbling, trumpeting, squeaking or roaring.
ST	Stereotyping	Standing still while moving forward or backwards. Bobbing head while standing still. Moving one leg in a forwards and backwards motion.
TU	Tool use	Scratching with stick, fly swatting with branch, throwing branch over body.
WA	Walking	Movement of all four legs in a forward or backward motion. Does not include walking towards food.

Table 2.2c. Behavioural ethogram for Calf Development

Code ID	Behaviour	Description
AT	Agitation	Showing signs of distress due to external factors (motorbike, other animal, loud sounds), that can be exhibited by walking chaotically, raising tail for 5 seconds or more and vocalizing as a form of stress.
DR	Drinking	Using trunk to take water and placing in mouth.
EI	Elephant interaction	Interacting with other individuals with touch of any body part (Not part of courtship behaviour).
FE	Foraging/ Exploring	Placing food in mouth, exploring environment to find new food. Walking towards food. Moving either the tip of the trunk or the whole trunk for practice or to search the ground for food or objects.
LD	Lying down	Lying down on the ground laterally.
LP	Lone play	Playing by himself (including rolling around on the ground or stomping in circles with no apparent objective, kicking, kneeling down on front legs) or with an object (playfully exploring objects with trunk or feet in a vigorous or gentle manner, and associated with playful head and ear movements).
MI	Mahout interaction / play	Any interaction with a mahout, solicited or spontaneous, including receiving food from mahout.
NV	Not visible	Behaviour cannot be recorded, elephant out of view, or cannot distinguish behaviour.
SM	Self-maintenance Behaviours	Bathing (whole body is immersed in water or having four limbs in water), Mud bathing (rolling in mud or using trunk to spray mud on body), dusting (collection of soil with trunk and throwing it over body), scratching (scratching or rubbing any body part with another part of the body or with an inanimate object).
ST	Stereotyping	Standing still while moving forward or backwards. Bobbing head while standing still. Moving one leg in a forwards and backwards motion.
SU	Suckling	Suckling milk from mother.
SV	Social vocalising	Communication such as rumbling, trumpeting, squeaking or roaring.
TU	Tool use	Scratching with stick, fly swatting with branch, throwing branch over body.
WA	Walking	Movement of all four legs in a forward or backward motion. Does not include walking towards food.

2.3. Results

Activity Time Budgets

Activity Time Budget data were collected on the five adult elephants at KSES for a total of 29,622 minutes of continuous data. The majority of these data were collected in the morning (26,217 minutes), 3,405 minutes were collected in the afternoon. Despite the variation in minutes from these two time periods, there was no significant difference in the behaviours of the elephants between morning and afternoon activity budgets ($F=1.09$, $p>0.05$). Table 2.3a shows the percentage of total minutes of all continuous data (i.e. behaviours performed for one minute or more) for the morning and afternoon observations. Out of the 18 behaviours listed in the behavioural ethogram, foraging was the most frequent behaviour displayed by the elephants during both the morning and the afternoon. Other frequent continuous behaviours included exploring, drinking, walking, dusting and mud bathing. All other behaviours were recorded less than 1% of the time. There were no observations of aggression, bathing or mating in the elephants (Table 2.3a, Figure 2.3a). The elephants were not visible for 12% of the time in the morning and 14% of the time in the afternoon. There was no significant difference in the continuous behaviours between the five elephants in the study ($F=0.192$, $p>0.05$). “Not visible” was excluded in the statistical analysis for all tests.

Table 2.3a: Average percentage of total minutes for continuous behaviours displayed by five adult elephants (N=5), in the morning and afternoon.

Behaviour	Percentage of total minutes for continuous behaviours	
	Morning	Afternoon
Foraging	73.98%	70.13%
Not Visible	11.73%	13.89%
Exploring	5.26%	5.08%
Drinking	2.22%	1.50%
Walking	1.93%	3.58%
Dusting	1.24%	0.85%
Mud Bathing	0.91%	1.88%
Elephant interaction	0.95%	0.91%
Scratching	0.51%	0.79%
Mahout interaction	0.46%	0.79%
Agitation	0.40%	0.35%
Social Vocalising	0.34%	0.18%
Stereotyping	0.03%	0.09%
Tool Use	0.03%	0.03%
Lying down	0.01%	0.00%
Aggression	0.00%	0.00%
Bathing	0.00%	0.00%
Mating	0.00%	0.00%

Figure 2.3a. Average frequency of continuous behaviours displayed by five adult elephants (N=5), in the morning and the afternoon

Instantaneous behaviours occur for less than one minute and are presented as count data rather than minutes. There was a total of 6,023 counts of instantaneous behaviours. 5,380 counts were recorded during morning observations and 643 counts were recorded during afternoon observations. There was a significant difference between the behaviours of the elephants between the morning and afternoon for instantaneous data ($F=4.493$, $p<0.05$). Table 2.3b shows the frequency of instantaneous behaviours performed by the elephants in the morning and afternoon time periods. The instantaneous data also shows more variation in the elephant behaviour, as all 18 behaviours were observed to some degree (Figure 2.3b), compared to the continuous data set where only 15 behaviours were observed (Figure 2.3a). Similar to the continuous dataset, foraging was the most frequent behaviour and exploring was the second highest. Other frequent instantaneous behaviours include dusting, walking, elephant interaction, scratching, social vocalising, agitation, mahout interaction, drinking, tool use and mud bathing. All other behaviours were observed at very low frequencies such as bathing, laying down, aggression and mating (Table 2.3b, Figure 2.3b). The elephants were not visible for 10% of the time during the morning observations and 13% during the afternoon observations. There was no significant difference in the instantaneous behaviours between the five elephants in the study ($F=2.03$, $p>0.05$). Furthermore, season or time of year did not have any effect on the Activity Time Budgets of the elephants ($F=0.243$, $p>0.05$). “Not visible” was excluded in the statistical analysis for all tests.

Table 2.3b. Average percentage of total number of counts for instantaneous behaviours displayed by five adult elephants (N=5), in the morning and afternoon.

Behaviour	Percentage of total minutes for continuous behaviours	
	Morning	Afternoon
Foraging	37.07%	35.30%
Exploring	12.79%	10.58%
Not Visible	10.30%	12.60%
Dusting	9.09%	4.82%
Walking	7.55%	11.35%
Elephant interaction	4.87%	4.20%
Scratching	3.85%	5.44%
Social Vocalising	3.12%	2.02%
Agitation	2.83%	1.71%
Mahout interaction	2.70%	2.64%
Drinking	2.08%	2.95%
Tool use	1.95%	0.93%
Mud bathing	1.51%	4.20%
Stereotyping	0.19%	0.93%
Bathing	0.04%	0.31%
Lying down	0.04%	0.00%
Aggression	0.02%	0.00%
Mating	0.02%	0.00%

Figure 2.3b. Average frequency of instantaneous behaviours displayed by five adult elephants (N=5), in the morning and the afternoon.

Foraging

A total of 7,089 minutes of foraging data were collected between all five elephants. Foraging data is not collected on the young calf, Junior. Figure 2.3c shows the frequency of time the elephants spent consuming either browse species (bamboo, climber, herb, shrub or tree), graze species (grasses) or new samples (unidentified plants by botanist, but identified by local Karen name). The elephants were observed consuming graze species (grasses) the most, at a percentage of 65.93%. The elephants consumed browse species for 33.50% of their time. They consumed 0.56% of new samples (Figure 2.3c). From the foraging data collected, 63 different plant species were consumed. Figure 2.3d shows that they spent the highest proportion of their time-consuming grass species (65.93%). There was a total of ten grass species identified and the most common grass consumed was *Pennisetum polystachion* (L.) Schult., (Noh gwah) at a rate of 34.70%. Bamboo was consumed at a frequency of 15.18% (Figure 2.3d). There were two species of bamboo identified, and the most common species eaten by the elephants is known as Vami in the local Karen language (13.63%, Table 2.3c). The elephants spent 6.90% of their time eating 28 different species of trees (Figure 2.3d). The preferred tree species was *Shorea obtusa* (Lah Boh) (2.71%, Table 2.3c). There were 14 different species of climbers identified and the elephants spent 6.43% eating climbers (Figure 2.3d), especially *Pueraria sp.*, (Gopomu) at a rate of 2.61% (Table 2.3c). There were six herb species identified that the elephants spent 4.99% of their time eating (Figure 2.3d). The most frequently consumed herb was an unidentified herb species known as Hoh duh hoh in the local Karen language (3.96%, Table 2.3c). The elephants spent the least amount of time consuming shrub species (0.56%, Figure 2.3d). A total of three species were recorded and the most popular one was in the Vitaceae family known as Lah nee in the local language at 0.34% (Table 2.3c). There was a statistically significant difference between the means of the five functional groups (see methods for details) ($F=3.92$, $p<0.05$). Season did not play a significant role in the elephants foraging behaviour in this study ($F=0.793$, $p>0.05$). There was no significant difference in foraging habits between the five elephants ($F=0.915$, $p>0.05$)

Figure 2.3c. Frequency of browse (bamboo, climber, herb, shrub, tree), graze (grasses) or new samples consumed by five adult elephants (N=5).

Figure 2.3d: Frequency of plants by their functional group consumed by five adult elephants (N=5).

Table 2.3c Plant species and parts consumed in percentages, classified under Karen (in parentheses) and botanical name in 2024.

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
(Vami) Poaceae	Other	Leaves, roots, shoot, stem, whole plant	13.63%
(Vasu) Poaceae	Other	Leaves, stem	1.55%
<i>Pachyrhizus sp.</i> (Bloor moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem	0.62%
<i>Pueraria sp.</i> (Gopomu) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem, twig, roots, whole plant	2.61%
<i>Tinospora sp.</i> (Duh suh key) Menispermaceae	Climber	Leaves, twig	0.28%
(Dah ugh juh moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem	0.01%
<i>Entada rheedii Spreng.</i> (Rey match uh) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves	0.07%
<i>Tinospora crispa</i> (Borapet) Menispermaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem	0.01%
<i>Mucuna sp.</i> (Bay moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves stem	0.34%
<i>Paederia foetida</i> (Chewie et non a moo) Rubiaceae	Climber	Leaves, stem, twig, whole plant	0.56%
<i>Dioscorea sp.</i> (New-ay me amoo) Dioscoreaceae	Climber	Leaves	0.10%
<i>Cissus sp.</i> (Qwa qwa moo) Vitaceae	Climber	Whole plant	0.23%
Unidentified (Guhsee padoh)	Climber	Leaves, stem, twig	0.04%
Unidentified (Paw me sah)	Climber	Leaves	0.04%
<i>Cissus hastata Miq.</i> (Pah gwah/ tah pah qwah) Vitaceae	Climber	Leaves	0.13%
<i>Sphatolobus sp.</i> (Qui bah moo) Fabaceae	Climber	Leaves, bark, roots, stem, twig, whole plant	1.38%
<i>Oryza sativa L.</i> (Mae) Poaceae	Grass	Whole plant	8.22%
<i>Zea mays</i> (Bukessa) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	9.28%

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
(Non check ko) Poaceae	Grass	Whole plant	2.19%
<i>Pennisetum polystachion</i> (L.) Schult. (Noh gwah) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, twig, whole plant	34.70%
(Noh rey) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	0.59%
(Geh meh or Gammay) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, whole plant	0.45%
(Neh pee-ah) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	9.18%
<i>Cyrtococcum accrescens</i> (Trin.) Stapf (Noh vah deh) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, whole plant	0.17%
Unidentified (Chew meh bwee) (Noh or Door moo) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	0.28%
Unidentified (Noh vee meh) Poaceae	Grass	Leaves, stem, whole plant	0.86%
Unidentified (Noh vee meh)	Herb	Leaves, stem	0.52%
Unidentified (Hoh duh doh)	Herb	Leaves, stem, shoot, whole plant	3.96%
(Puh) Zingiberaceae	Herb	Whole plant	0.02%
<i>Cheilocostus speciosus</i> (Le bow) Costaceae	Herb	Leaves, stem	0.07%
<i>Crassocephalum crepidioides</i> (Benth.) S. Moore (Duh boo dah) Asteraceae	Herb	Whole plant	0.24%
<i>Commelina paludosa</i> Blume (Goh poh doh) Commelinaceae	Herb	Whole plant	0.16%
<i>Solanum erianthum</i> D. Don (Suh gloh pluh) Solanaceae	Shrub	Whole plant	0.04%
<i>Solanum torvum</i> Sw. (Suh go caw) Solanaceae	Shrub	Leaves, whole plant	0.18%
(Lah nee) Vitaceae	Shrub	Leaves, stem, bark	0.34%
<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb. (Say juh nah) Lecythidaceae	Tree	Fruit	0.11%
<i>Broussonetia papyrifera</i> (L.) L'Her. Ex Vent. (Sah lay dah) Moraceae	Tree	Bark	0.01%
<i>Ficus subpisocarpa</i> Gagnep. (Kluh lah) Moraceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, twig	0.08%
Unidentified (Say beh me)	Tree	Bark	0.01%
<i>Archidendron</i> sp. (Poat du sue or Say duh) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.24%
<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Da ooch oo moo) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem	0.32%
(Poca) Rubiaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark	0.25%
<i>Albizia</i> sp. (Buchee) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem, twig, bark	0.21%
(Dah sway) Tiliaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.04%
<i>Tectona grandis</i> (Buh he) Lamiaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.17%

Plant	Type	Part(s) consumed	% of foraging encounters
<i>Musa spp.</i> (Suh qwee) Musaceae	Tree	Bark	0.97%
<i>Solanum erianthum</i> D. Don (Say goh plu) Solanaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.04%
<i>Radermachera</i> (La bodeh) Araliaceae/Bignoniaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.07%
<i>Aporosa sp.</i> (Say pro prii) Phyllanthaceae	Tree	Leaves, roots	0.14%
<i>Gluta usitata</i> (Wall.) Ding Hou (Su) Anacardiaceae	Tree	Leaves, stem, twig, bark	0.01%
<i>Shorea obtusa</i> (Lah boh) Dipterocarpaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, roots	2.71%
<i>Quercus kerrii</i> Craib (Sah gay prah) Fagaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.01%
<i>Dipterocarpus tuberculatus</i> Roxb. (La tuh) Dipterocarpaceae	Tree	Leaves, twig, bark, stem	0.25%
<i>Ficus sp.</i> (Dah ooh nah) Moraceae	Tree	Leaves	0.23%
<i>Quercus sp.</i> (Say) Fagaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.00%
<i>Bauhinia sp.</i> (Guh huh) Fabaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.04%
<i>Grewia eriocarpa</i> Juss. (Sah bloh bley) Tiliaceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, twig	0.01%
<i>Sterculia foetida</i> L. (Koh) Malvaceae	Tree	Bark, twig	0.24%
Unidentified (Suh duh)	Tree	Bark	0.35%
<i>Lagerstroemia sp.</i> (Duh koh ha) Lythraceae	Tree	Leaves, twigs	0.06%
<i>Protium serratum</i> Engl. (Suh pee) Burseraceae	Tree	Leaves, bark, twig, stem	0.11%
<i>Tamarindus indica</i> (Samoclay) Fabaceae	Tree	Fruit	0.01%
<i>Phoenix loureiroi</i> Kunth (Lee kaw doo) Arecaceae	Tree	Leaves	0.16%

Social Association

From analysing the Social Association dataset, we found that the female elephants were quite social. Too Meh, the oldest elephant at KSES, has associations with all members of the herd. She had a total of 1,589 data points for nearest neighbour associations and 759 data points for next nearest neighbour associations. Most of her nearest neighbour associations were with her daughter Mae Doom (75.27%). She spent the least amount of time near Junior (2.71%) (Figure 2.3e, Table 2.3d). Too Meh's next nearest neighbour associations were much more varied. She spent between 10-36% of her time in the presence of the other herd members, again, most frequently with Mae Doom (36.49%). She spent over half of her time at distances greater than six metres from the rest of the herd for both nearest neighbour and next nearest neighbour associations (53.59% and 71.28%, respectively).

Similarly, Mae Doom had associations with many of the other elephants and also had a large number of data points (1,732 for nearest neighbour and 945 for next nearest neighbour associations). She spent just over half of her nearest neighbour associations with her mother, Too Meh (56.64%). She also spent a lot of time with Sri Prai (17.64%) and Junior (13.22%). She spent some time with the males, although much less frequently (Dodo, 6.81% and Boon Rott, 5.66%) (Figure 2.3f, Table 2.3d). Mae Doom's next nearest neighbour associations were also divided between all elephants. Most frequently with Sri Prai (30.39%) and Too Meh (30.08%), but also with the males Boon Rott (17.18%) and Dodo (12.61%). Most of her nearest neighbour associations and next nearest neighbour associations were within three metres distance from another individual or greater than six metres.

Figure 2.3e. Too Meh's nearest neighbour associations in relation to the rest of the herd.

Figure 2.3f. Mae Doom's nearest neighbour associations in relation to the rest of the herd.

Sri Prai is also quite a social elephant. She had the highest number of data points for nearest neighbour associations (1,810) and next nearest neighbour associations (1,090). Most of her nearest neighbour associations were with her calf, Junior (44.97%), followed Junior's father, Dodo (22.04%), and she spent 19.01% of her time with Mae Doom. She spent the least amount of time with Too Meh (2.38%) and had very few associations with Boon Rott (0.61%) (Figure 2.3g, Table 2.3d). Almost half of Sri Prai's next nearest neighbour associations were with Dodo (46.57%). The majority of Sri Prai's nearest neighbour associations occurred within three metres distance (45.36%) and the majority of her next nearest neighbour associations occurred at distances greater than six metres (45.78%).

Figure 2.3g. Sri Prai's nearest neighbour associations in relation to the rest of the herd.

From the data collected on our male elephants we saw that they were less social and did not spend as much time with the rest of the herd when compared to the females. Boon Rott spent the least amount of time with the herd and he had the fewest number of association counts for both nearest neighbour and next nearest neighbour (536 and 494 counts, respectively). Boon Rott had the largest number of associations with Too Meh (43.28%), followed by Mae Doom (36.38%) and Dodo (10.26%) (Figure 2.3h, Table 2.3d). Boon Rott's next nearest neighbour associations were mainly with Mae Doom (49.90%), followed by Too Meh (24.85%) and Sri Prai (13.21%). Boon Rott had no occurrences of touching another elephant in the next nearest neighbour dataset. The majority of Boon Rott's associations for nearest neighbour and next nearest neighbour occurred at distances greater than six metres (76.12% and 90.89%, respectively).

Figure 2.3h. Boon Rott's nearest neighbour associations in relation to the rest of the herd.

Dodo had 1,299 data points for nearest neighbour associations and 480 data points for next nearest neighbour associations. There was more variation in Dodo's associations than Boon Rott; his nearest neighbour and next nearest neighbour associations were very similar. For nearest neighbour, he associated the most with Sri Prai (62.59%) and Junior (18.24%), followed by Mae Doom (18.24%) (Figure 2.3i, Table 2.3d). Dodos next nearest neighbours were also Sri Prai (40.56%), Junior (32.68%) and Mae Doom (16.22%). Most of Dodo's associations with the herd for both nearest neighbour and next nearest neighbour occurred at distances greater than six metres (48.96% and 59.40%, respectively).

Figure 2.3i. Dodo's nearest neighbour associations in relation to the rest of the herd.

Junior associated at much closer distances with the herd, as expected from a young calf. Junior had a total of 987 data points for nearest neighbour associations and 808 data points for next nearest neighbour associations. His nearest neighbour was mostly his mother Sri Prai (72.14%, Figure 2.3j) and his next nearest neighbour was mostly his father Dodo (48.76%). He also associated closely with his great-aunt Mae Doom (15.92% for nearest neighbour and 18.19% for next nearest neighbour) (Table 2.3d). Junior spent one third (33.03%) of his nearest neighbour associations directly interacting or touching these elephants and around half of his time within three metres (50.15%) of them.

Figure 2.3j. Junior's nearest neighbour associations in relation to the rest of the herd.

Table 2.3d: Nearest neighbour associations between herd members 2024.

	Nearest neighbour	Next nearest neighbour
Too Meh - Boon Rott	7.93%	18.80%
Too Meh - Dodo	6.93%	10.34%
Too Meh - Junior	2.71%	11.83%
Too Meh - Mae Doom	75.27%	36.49%
Too Meh - Sri Prai	7.68%	22.54%
Mae Doom - Boon Rott	5.66%	17.18%
Mae Doom - Dodo	6.81%	12.61%
Mae Doom - Junior	13.22%	7.75%
Mae Doom - Sri Prai	17.64%	30.39%
Mae Doom - Too Meh	56.64%	32.08%
Sri Prai - Boon Rott	0.61%	2.25%
Sri Prai - Dodo	22.04%	45.67%
Sri Prai - Junior	44.97%	11.79%
Sri Prai - Mae Doom	19.01%	27.30%
Sri Prai - Too Meh	2.38%	13.00%
Boon Rott - Dodo	10.26%	9.07%
Boon Rott - Junior	0.93%	2.96%
Boon Rott - Mae Doom	36.38%	49.90%
Boon Rott - Sri Prai	9.14%	13.21%
Boon Rott - Too Meh	43.28%	24.85%
Dodo - Boon Rott	1.62%	2.67%
Dodo - Junior	18.24%	32.68%
Dodo - Mae Doom	18.24%	16.22%
Dodo - Sri Prai	62.59%	40.56%
Dodo - Too Meh	5.54%	7.88%
Junior - Boon Rott	0.10%	0.12%
Junior - Dodo	9.83%	48.76%
Junior - Mae Doom	15.92%	18.19%
Junior - Sri Prai	72.14%	28.09%
Junior - Too Meh	2.03%	4.83%

Calf Development

A total of 5,629 minutes of continuous data were collected for calf development. Of these, 4,970 minutes of data were collected during morning observations and 659 minutes of data were collected during afternoon observations. There was no significant difference in behaviour between the morning and afternoon observations ($F=1.24$, $p>0.05$). Out of the 14 behaviours listed on the calf development ethogram, the most frequent continuous behaviour Junior displayed during the morning hikes was foraging/exploring at 53.32%. The next most frequent behaviour was mahout interaction (3.98%), self-maintenance (2.07%), walking (1.75%), elephant interaction (1.73%), lone play (1.39%) and suckling (1.31%). Other behaviours occurred at frequencies less than 1% (drinking, lying down, agitation, seeking rescue, social vocalising and tool use) (Figure 2.3k, Table 2.3e). Similarly, the most frequent continuous behaviour displayed in the afternoon is foraging/exploring at 43.40%. The next most frequent behaviours observed during the afternoon were walking (6.37%), self-maintenance (5.46%), elephant interaction (3.79%), mahout interaction (3.64%), suckling (1.67%). The other behaviours that occurred at frequencies less than 1% were drinking and laying down. Agitation, seeking rescue, social vocalising and tool use were not observed during the afternoon (Figure 2.3k, Table 2.3e) and stereotypic behaviours were not observed at all in the young calf. Junior was not visible 32.70% of the time in the morning and 33.84% of the time during afternoon data collection. "Not visible" was excluded from all statistical tests.

Table 2.3e: Percentage of continuous behaviours displayed by Junior (N=1), in the morning and the afternoon.

Behaviour	Percentage of total minutes for continuous behaviours	
	Morning	Afternoon
Foraging/exploring	53.32%	43.40%
Not visible	32.70%	33.84%
Mahout interaction	3.98%	3.64%
Self-maintenance	2.07%	5.46%
Walking	1.75%	6.37%
Elephant interaction	1.73%	3.79%
Lone play	1.39%	1.06%
Suckling	1.31%	1.67%
Drinking	0.89%	0.61%
Lying down	0.48%	0.15%
Agitation	0.14%	0.00%
Seeking rescue	0.12%	0.00%
Social vocalising	0.08%	0.00%
Tool use	0.04%	0.00%
Stereotyping	0.00%	0.00%

Figure 2.3k: Frequency of continuous behaviours displayed by Junior (N=1), in the morning and afternoon.

Behaviours that were displayed for less than one minute were categorised as instantaneous behaviours. There were 1,821 counts during morning observations and 240 counts during the afternoon observations, resulting a total of 2,061 counts of behaviours. There was no significance difference between morning and afternoon behaviours for instantaneous behaviours ($F=3.67$, $p>0.05$). The most frequent instantaneous behaviour during the morning was foraging/exploring at 38.71%, followed by mahout interaction (10.27%), elephant interaction (9.23%), walking (5.99%), self-maintenance (5.33%), lone play and suckling (2.91%), seeking rescue (2.31%) and drinking (1.37%). Behaviours that occurred at frequencies of less than 1% were lying down, social vocalising, tool use and agitation (Figure 2.3l, Table 2.3f). Similarly, the most frequent instantaneous behaviour displayed by Junior in the afternoon was foraging/exploring (30.42%). The next most frequent behaviours were elephant interaction (12.50%), walking (11.67%), self-maintenance (9.58%), mahout interaction (7.08%), suckling (3.33%), drinking and lone play (both 2.08%). Three instantaneous behaviours occurred at a frequency of 0.83% and these were lying down, seeking rescue and social vocalising. Agitation and tool use were not observed during afternoon observations (Figure 2.3l, Table 2.3f). Similar to the continuous dataset, no stereotypic behaviours were observed. Junior was not visible for 18.01% of the time for in the morning and 18.75% during the afternoon. “Not visible” was excluded from all statistical tests.

Table 2.3f. Percentage of total number of counts for instantaneous behaviours displayed by Junior (N=1), in the morning and afternoon.

Behaviour	Percentage of total count for instantaneous behaviours	
	Morning	Afternoon
Foraging/exploring	38.71%	30.42%
Not visible	18.01%	18.75%
Mahout interaction	10.27%	7.08%
Elephant interaction	9.23%	12.50%
Walking	5.99%	11.67%
Self-maintenance	5.33%	9.58%
Lone play	2.91%	2.08%
Suckling	2.91%	3.33%
Seeking rescue	2.31%	0.83%
Drinking	1.37%	2.08%
Lying down	0.88%	0.83%
Social vocalising	0.82%	0.83%
Tool use	0.77%	0.00%
Agitation	0.49%	0.00%
Stereotyping	0.00%	0.00%

Figure 2.3f. Frequency of instantaneous behaviours displayed by Junior (N=1), in the morning and afternoon.

2.4. Discussion and conclusions

Activity Time Budget

From the Activity Time Budget dataset, foraging was recorded at the highest frequency for both the continuous and instantaneous observations. Elephants in the wild can forage for 60-80% of their day (Ahamed 2015, Baker & Winkler 2020, Vanitha et al. 2010). Conversely many elephants in captive settings across Asia and in Western zoos do not forage at similar frequencies to their wild counterparts (Bansiddhi et al. 2019, Greco et al., 2016). At KSES, the elephants are free-roaming throughout the day, thus giving them the opportunity to forage as they would in the wild, which is reflected in the data. Foraging naturally is vital for elephant health and wellbeing as it strengthens trunk muscles, promotes walking to find food and exploring their environment to allow them to exhibit problem-solving behaviours (Veasey 2019). Many zoos worldwide have begun to add more natural and less predictable foraging strategies, and as a result there is an increase in elephant locomotion and a decrease in stereotypic behaviours (Greco et al. 2016, Rees, 2009). Stereotypic behaviours are abnormal behaviours and can be indicative of present or past trauma in animals (Fuktong et al. 2021, Greco et al. 2017). The elephants in this study showed stereotypic behaviours at very low frequencies. We therefore conclude that free-roaming elephants who are able to display a wider variety of behaviours in a forest environment and are allowed to socialise with their conspecifics show much reduced stereotypic behaviours.

It has been shown that elephants in different captive regimes show variation in the prevalence of stereotypies due to varying levels of confinement (Varadharajan et al. 2016, Fuktong et al. 2021). Elephants in temples and riding camps show high stereotypic behaviours while elephants that have more freedom to roam in the forest show fewer stereotypic behaviours (Varadharajan et al. 2016). However, it must be noted that elephants do have a tendency to stereotype more often during the night when there are fewer opportunities to forage and socialise than during the day time (Rees 2009). The present report does not contain any data of the nighttime behaviours of the elephants at KSES and therefore we cannot rule out that the elephants may be stereotyping to some degree throughout the night. It has also been seen that stereotypic behaviour is more prevalent in young bulls if they cannot develop strong bonds and do not have the ability to socialise properly (Varadharajan et al. 2016, Webber 2017). While some of the elephants in this study have spent many years in isolation, they now have the opportunity to socialise as they please, which may be one of the reasons why stereotypic behaviours are not commonly observed during the morning and afternoon observations.

From analysing the Activity Time Budget data, there is much more variation in the instantaneous dataset compared to the continuous dataset and all 18 behaviours from the behavioural ethogram were observed to some degree. Elephants in more restricted settings may not typically show such variation in their behaviour as they can often be more restricted in their movements and expression of natural behaviours (Baker & Winkler 2020, Varadharajan et al. 2016). An opportunity to display a wide variety of behaviours supports good physical and psychological wellbeing in elephants (Bansiddhi et al. 2020).

While foraging and exploring remain the most common behaviours displayed even at the instantaneous level, dusting was the third most frequent behaviour. Dusting is an important part in an elephant's behavioural repertoire as it protects their skin from radiation and insect bites, as well as playing a role in temperature regulation (Rees 2002).

Elephant interaction was also observed at a high frequency in the instantaneous dataset. As a highly social species, frequent contact with other elephants is paramount to their welfare. In captivity, not being able to socialise with other elephants or being placed in appropriate social groupings can lead to negative elephant welfare (Schreier et al. 2021).

Foraging

The elephants showed a preference for graze species over browse species. This is in contrast to previous findings from foraging results at KSES where the elephants have shown a preference for browse species, particularly bamboo (Schwarz et al. 2020). Previous reports have also shown, however, that the percentage of bamboo that the elephants consume fluctuates each year. For example, in 2023 the elephants ate almost 50% bamboo, but in 2019 the elephants ate 15% bamboo. The results of this study are similar to the 2019 statistic, where bamboo made up a smaller proportion of the elephant diet. The preference for graze over browse also changes depending on the season (Roy & Chowdhury 2014). For example, elephants consume more graze species during the dry seasons and consume more bamboo during the rainy seasons (Schwarz et al. 2020). While we did not see any significant difference in what the elephants consumed over the three seasons in the present study, it must be noted that the number of minutes of foraging data was not equal throughout the year, with the majority of foraging data collected in the cold season and rainy season compared to the hot season. This may have had an impact on the data as the location of the elephants in the forest and ultimately their foraging habits changes throughout the year. The elephants at KSES live in a unique environment where there is a combination of natural forest for them to roam in as well as community forest, which includes some cultivated grass fields and some agricultural land (Schwarz et al. 2020). By working closely with the local people in the surrounding villages, the elephants have the opportunity to forage in many different environments throughout the year (Schwarz et al. 2020). Having the freedom to exhibit preferences on what to consume on a daily basis contributes to elephant welfare. The diets of elephants in captivity can vary greatly. In western zoos the main component of the diet is hay with the addition of other browse species. In Thailand, many captive elephants are fed sugarcanes, bananas and other foods containing large amounts of sugar (Rees 2009, Veasey 2019, Bansiddhi et al. 2019). Unsuitable diets, those with a lack of variation or irregular feeding times can lead to health issues in elephants (Baker & Winkler 2020). Therefore, by providing an adequate and more natural diet for elephants as well as allowing elephants to roam and move around for preferred foods, allows them to expend energy while they are consuming food, which can help to reduce health related issues such as malnutrition, obesity and diabetes (Veasey 2019, Bansiddhi et al. 2020, Rees 2009).

Furthermore, the number of new plant species observed in the data also increases each year, highlighting the importance of long-term studies. Continuing the foraging dataset at KSES is paramount as shown here, as it not only helps to spread awareness about the variation in elephant diet, but also about the high plant biodiversity that exists in the area (Schwarz et al. 2020).

Social Association

Asian elephants live in multilevel matriarchal societies, comprised of females and their offspring (de Silva & Wittemyer 2012, Bonaparte-Saller & Mench 2018). Therefore, it is not surprising that Too Meh, Mae Doom and Sri Prai spent a lot of time with each other and also around the young calf, while the male elephants spent less time with the rest of the herd. It can be said that the female elephants at KSES, in general, are behaving in a very similar manner to wild elephants, forming close bonds with each other. Too Meh and Mae Doom, a mother and daughter reunited in 2016 when brought to KSES after living apart for many years, spend much of their time in the company of one another, indicating a strong bond between them. More recently, Mae Doom has also been seeking out the company of Sri Prai since the birth of Junior. It is very natural in wild Asian elephant societies for females to help each other when calves are around, providing support and opportunities for social learning (de Silva & Wittemyer 2012, Webber, 2017). As expected, Sri Prai, as a new mother, spends most of her close social associations with her young calf, as elephants invest a lot of time in their young. Females provide milk for their calves until they are three or four years old while also teaching the calf the social and foraging skills (Vanitha et al. 2011, Petraccione et al. 2017, Webber, 2017).

Generally, in the wild, when males reach 10-14 years old, they leave their natal herd and live alone or in loose bachelor groups (de Silva & Wittemyer 2012, Thevarajah et al. 2021, Webber 2017). Furthermore, male elephants typically do not stay to form any bonds with females they have mated with or get involved in parental care (Thevarajah et al. 2021). By contrast, at KSES, Dodo continues to exhibit a close relationship with Sri Prai and their calf Junior. While this is not commonly seen in wild elephants, it has been observed in some male elephants living in captivity where they maintain bonds with both the mother and calf (Webber 2017). Dodo also associates closely with his aunt, which is also quite unusual for male elephants. As discussed in the previous section, the elephants at KSES are generally behaving in a way similar to wild elephants in many aspects such as foraging, but one must take into consideration the life histories and previous experiences that these elephants may have had before being brought to KSES, including much social isolation. It has been shown that improper socialisation can have long-lasting effects on elephants, and may result in different affiliations with other individuals not typically seen in their wild counterparts (Webber 2017). Junior, the calf of Sri Prai and Dodo, spends his closest associations with his mother and his next nearest neighbour associations with his father. Again, this type of relationship is not typical for wild calves, but does occur in captivity (Petraccione et al. 2017). Bonding with the father and other male elephants can have a developmental advantage for young calves (Webber 2017). Similarly, spending time with other females in the herd, such as Mae Doom, and learning from them, is also very beneficial for a young calf (Petraccione et al. 2017, Webber, 2017). Boon Rott had the least social interactions out of all members in the herd at KSES. This is not surprising, given that he is a 19 year old bull and also unrelated to the rest of the herd (de Silva & Wittemyer 2012, Thevarajah et al. 2023). However, occasionally he seeks the company of Too Meh and Mae Doom. A possible reason for this is that he was brought to KSES at the same time as the two females and developed a strong bond with them as they explored the forest together. Eight years have passed since this introduction to the forest, and while these interactions have become fewer over time, he still seeks the company of his other herd members from time to time.

Calf Development

The newest dataset deployed at KSES is Calf Development. In this dataset, the behaviours of foraging and exploring were combined, in contrast to the Activity Time Budget dataset for the adult elephants, as it allows for more seamless observations. Young elephants lack a strong ability to perform competent movements for up to one year, and foraging activity is often combined with exploration as they develop and practise the fine motor skills in their trunk (Webber 2017).

Foraging/exploring was the most frequent behaviour the calf displayed, with Junior spending approximately half of his time engaged in this behaviour. While this is lower than the adult elephants in this study, it is to be expected that a young elephant spends less time focused on one particular behaviour, as they are extremely curious about their surroundings.

Junior also spent a high proportion of his time engaged in self-maintenance behaviours, especially in the afternoon. This includes mud bathing, dusting, scratching and bathing, all of which are important behaviours to learn. It has been reported that well-developed dusting behaviours can be seen in calves by one year old (Webber 2017). This suggests that Junior is reaching these pivotal milestones in his development on time.

While foraging and exploring is a common activity, for a calf of this age, suckling is a vital behaviour to monitor in the development of young calves as they receive nourishment from their mother's milk, which is essential to their survival, supporting their immune system and the development of normal functions in the gut (Webber, 2017). Junior was observed suckling during the morning and afternoon in continuous behaviours for longer than one minute as well as instantaneous feeding bouts. Observing this important behaviour indicates that Junior is also receiving these important nutrients for his overall health and wellbeing. Furthermore, when a young elephant's basic needs are met through foraging, suckling and drinking, they can invest time in social and play behaviours which are also important for their development (Ahamed 2015, Bansiddhi et al. 2019, Webber 2017). This includes interaction with other elephants as learning appropriate social behaviours and maintaining social bonds are paramount in elephant societies as young elephants learn from imitating adult elephants (Petraccione et al. 2017, Webber 2017).

Junior was observed not only interacting with other elephants, but also with the mahouts. For many captive elephants, forming bonds with their mahouts is very important as they can be sources of comfort and protection and they can also assist in the preparation of essential vet care through target training elephants, a method which reduces stress during these procedures (Liehrmann et al. 2021, Crawley et al. 2024).

Lone play was also observed in both the morning and afternoon data collection time periods. Webber (2017) reports that some elephant calves in captivity spend more time in play behaviour than their wild counterparts. As Junior is free to express natural behaviours in the forest, surrounded by his family and other herd members, he can also engage in higher frequencies of play than wild elephants.

Conclusions and Future Directions

The partnership between KSES and Biosphere Expeditions from 2017 to 2024 contributed to significant scientific data collection on the resident elephant herd. Having a team of citizen scientists working together to collect data on all elephants simultaneously, as well as at various time throughout the day, furthered the KSES mission and goal to improve the welfare of elephants in captivity. The results of this and previous reports show that the aims of the four datasets that citizen scientists and research interns participate in when they come to KSES were met.

The reports have shown that by monitoring the behaviour of elephants in the Activity Time Budget dataset, elephants, which have been brought back to a natural forest environment, can indeed display behaviours that are more similar to their wild counterparts than to elephants in more controlled captive regimes.

The reports have also shown from the Foraging dataset that there is significant variation in the diet of the KSES elephants, not only in the number of species recorded, but also from year to year when data are compared across expedition reports.

The reports also provide important information about elephant associations and social groupings via the Social Association dataset. This dataset provides valuable data not only on the existing relationships between the herd members, but also on how these relationships evolve and change over time with the integration of new elephants in the herd.

Lastly, as KSES continues to grow and evolve as an organisation, the addition of a new dataset on Calf Development is an important addition.

In summary, we highlight the importance of long-term studies to create an accurate representation of how elephants respond to returning to a controlled, free-roaming life in the forest. These findings will contribute to future publications in the scientific literature. The next step is to publish the Activity Time Budget data in a peer-reviewed journal in 2025 and an elephant welfare guideline manual in 2026. We hope that providing scientific evidence about improvements in captive elephant welfare from this alternative model of elephant existence in Thailand, highlighting the importance of ethical elephant tourism, will not only spread more awareness and contribute to a positive change regarding the tourism situation in Thailand, but also improve the health and welfare of elephants in Thailand and beyond.

The unique setting at KSES allows researchers and citizen scientist to follow a herd of semi-wild Asian elephants and track their natural behaviours, foraging habits and social associations in the forest. Furthermore, working alongside the local community inspires positive changes in how elephants can be managed in captivity and showcasing that elephants and people can coexist in a harmonious way.

The expeditions run by Biosphere Expeditions have contributed significantly to these positive changes. Partnering with dedicated teams of citizen scientists each year has been wholly beneficial to furthering the goals of KSES and that of elephant conservation in Thailand and Asia.

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